

Living Lab in making: Exploring the emergent phase of University Living Lab development

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to explore the emergent phase of a university living lab to identify and explain the contingencies that surface from the process of developing and implementing an idea of a living lab in an already complicated institutional environment. The empirical research followed a single case study design. The analysis of the data gathered from multiple primary and secondary sources was guided by the qualitative content analysis approach. The study provides insights into behavioural, social, and cultural factors that underlie the emergence of a university living lab. It contributes to theory and practice by explaining the pre-lab dynamics and its context.

Key words

Living lab, university living lab, pre-lab, emergent phase

Objectives

Two decades of scholarly studies into living labs (Følstad, 2008; Ballon & Schuurman, 2015; Leminen & Westerlund, 2019) produced a wealth of knowledge and insights into how living labs can be utilized as a means of fostering innovation, engaging stakeholders, and promoting sustainable development (Hossain, Leminen & Westerlund, 2019). The research has identified various design principles, as well as different approaches to their governance and management (Leminen & Westerlund, 2019). While a systematically growing number of studies have enriched the understanding of components and processes that constitute living labs, there is a lack of works providing insights into the pre-lab dynamics to shed light on how a living lab becomes established. Acknowledging that living labs are generally understood as open innovation ecosystems (<https://enoll.org/about-us/>), their very logic builds on interdependence and coordination that leads to new value creation, and inherent variability in the configuration of internal attributes of ecosystems (Spigel, 2017) emphasizes the fact that there are multiple ways living labs can develop. Hence, as an ecosystem, a living lab does not necessarily emerge as a fully designed institutional project from the outset. The formal institutional framework can be developed in a non-linear fashion through complex interactions and experimentation with new ideas and approaches (Singh & Gurumurthy, 2013; Gancarczyk et al., 2023). Moreover, the practices used by actors to implement ideas may involuntarily change their meaning while institutionalizing them (McCarthy, 2009). Therefore, it is necessary to untangle the behavioural, social, and cultural factors that underlie the emergence of living labs.

The aim of this study is to explore the emergence phase of a university living lab to identify and explain the contingencies that surface from the process of developing and implementing an idea of living lab in an already complicated institutional environment. The theoretical foundations of our study focused on the processes of ongoing evolution within a system are the multi-actor network perspective of the ecosystem concept (Tsujiimoto et al., 2018), the institutional view (Green et al., 2009) and evolutionary perspective (Martin, 2010). Thus, our study makes a contribution to the body of knowledge on living labs by focusing on the largely overlooked emergence stage of their development, and by shifting the discussion beyond the mere description of successful, role model case studies toward the exploration of ways to foster development and improvement of homegrown ecosystem solutions based on the realities of own circumstances.

Approach

The empirical research followed a single case study design. The selected case was the Campus Living Lab (CaliLab) established at Jagiellonian University (Poland). In order to restore the behavioral, social, and cultural underpinnings of CaliLab emergence, the study design included an expanded set of research methods:

- First, we focused on analyzing the existing official documents of two initiatives: Kampus+ and "Research for practice. The use of master's implementation theses based on action research for the development of organizations" project. These initiatives were among the first steps towards the creation of the university's collaborative model with the environment. Our analysis included internal project documentation, as well as the official website and social media channels of the Kampus+ initiative.
- In the next stage we conducted in-depth interviews with people involved in the Kampus+ and "Research for practice" project to understand how the idea developed over time.
- Then we analyzed official documents developed in the process of design and formalization of CaliLab initiative, incl. project proposals, official correspondence with university officials.
- Finally, we applied the method of auto-ethnography to investigate the design process of CaliLab.

Given the focus of the study, the retrieved data referred to behavioural, social, and cultural factors that influence the development of the innovation ecosystem, which subsequently evolves into a living lab. The analysis of the gathered data was guided by the qualitative content analysis approach. The iterative process involved meaning-making, synthesizing, theorizing, and re-contextualizing. At present, the analysis is not yet concluded, and the work is still in progress.

Findings

The research is currently underway; hence the final results are not available at the moment. However, at this stage we already track the key interaction patterns. The activities that led to the launch of the Campus Living Lab were multifaceted. At the same

time, several initiatives and projects have been implemented over the last few years. Importantly, most of these activities were bottom-up and initiated by employees. One example was the project 'Research for practise. The use of master's implementation theses based on action research for the development of organizations', implemented between 2017 and 2019 by students and employees of the Faculty of Management and Social Communication of the Jagiellonian University in cooperation with public and nongovernmental organizations.

The project were (1) to implement practical MA theses, based on the Action Research approach to the practice of the Faculty and (2) to test the university's collaborative model with the environment. In Poland there is a lack of commitment and cultural orientation towards cooperation with business and other organizations (Bogacz-Wojtanowska, Jedynak, Wrona and Pluszyńska, 2019). Polish university managers and academics generally assess themselves and their environment as one of the least orientated to cooperate with business, public, and non-governmental organizations in Europe (Davey et al. 2013). For us, it was an important step toward the implementation of scientific activities in greater participation with the environment and getting closer to the quadruple helix model.

In other departments of the University at the same time, other activities aimed at change were launched. One of these initiatives was Kampus+, a grassroots movement established by students, PhD candidates, and academics at Jagiellonian University in the first half of 2017. Its goal was to spark a conversation on the quality and sustainability of public spaces on the university campus (Działek et al. 2021). The initiative sought to share knowledge on current trends and best practices for designing and managing these spaces, particularly with respect to the concept of a learning landscape. This concept reflects recent shifts in research and education, emphasizing collaborative efforts, informal knowledge exchange, and co-creation using both digital and physical resources (Backman et al. 2019; Cox et al. 2022).

Kampus+ engaged in scientific activities such as campus space studies, educational activities like lectures and workshops, and outreach activities such as seminars, study visits, and cooperative endeavours such as planting actions. As a result of coalition-building efforts, the initiative began collaborating with partners from within and outside the university, leading to small-scale test projects like outdoor seating areas and green spaces that linked social activities with biodiversity preservation. One of its most recent outcomes was a strategic plan for the public spaces of the campus, which proposed using

living labs as a tool for their development, among other proposals.

Kampus+ successfully ignited the conversation on the previously overlooked aspects of campus life. However, as a bottom-up enterprise, it was unable to take action on a larger scale. Thus, there was a need to integrate it into the wider inter-faculty and interdisciplinary structures of a living lab.

When the possibility of internal funding of projects appeared in the university, the willingness to undertake joint action arose among the implementers of the above-mentioned projects. The concept of a joint initiative, Campus Living Lab, was built on the basis of the experience gained from two different projects implemented at different faculties.

Value and implications

Our study contributes to the body of knowledge on generation of living lab projects (Evans et al., 2015). Focusing on the pre-lab stage fills the gap as most of the research on living labs concentrates on the full-scale phase. The study provides insights into complex interactions involving re-tooling the campus from a passive to an active environment for teaching and learning. It helps to understand how dispersed initiatives across university units can become integrated into a legitimized and institutionalized ecosystem of a living lab.

The experience of Jagiellonian University in the implementation of CaliLab can be valuable for universities struggling with providing institutional anchoring for cross-disciplinary, multi-level, and multi-stakeholder projects. It can also inform other organizations implementing projects aimed at boosting innovation processes that require the involvement and activation of many diverse stakeholders, as well as inspire further work on universities and their ways to foster the development and improvement of homegrown ecosystem solutions based on the realities of own circumstances.

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